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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF NUTRACEUTICAL
GUMMIES FROM WOODAPPLE AND FENUGREEK FOR
TYPE 2 DIABETIC****Vaishnavi K. Gandhi¹, Nandakishor B Deshmukh², Dr. Swati P. Deshmukh³**¹ Students, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Kondala Zambre, Washim² Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy,
Kondala Zambre, Washim³ Principal, Department of Pharmacology Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Kondala Zambre,
Washim**Abstract:**

*The development and evaluation of nutraceutical gummies incorporating fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*) and woodapple (*Limonia acidissima*) Form the central focus of this study. Diabetes mellitus particularly type 2 diabetes is a chronic metabolic disorder characterised by persistent hyperglycaemia resulting from impaired insulin secretion insulin resistance or both. The increase global prevalence of diabetes has created a growing demand for safer more effective and patient friendly therapeutic approaches.*

In recent years there has been noticeable shift towards the use of plant based nutraceuticals as supportive management options for chronic diseases. Traditional medicinal plants such as fenugreek and wood apple have gained significant attention due to their well documented pharmacological activities. Fenugreek is known for its ability to improve glucose tolerance and reduce insulin resistance, while wood apple exhibits antioxidant anti hyperglycemic and lipid lowering properties. These natural agents offer a promising alternative or adjacent to conventional anti diabetic therapies. Despite their therapeutic benefits the acceptability of arbal formulations is often limited by conventional dosage forms like tablets and capsules which may lead to poor patient compliance. To overcome this limitation, The present study explores the formulation of nutraceutical gummies as an innovative and user friendly delivery system. Gummies are particularly advantageous due to their palatability ease of administration and improved patient adherence.

In this study 3 different formulations (F1, F2, and F3) were prepared using varying concentrations of excipients such as Agar citric acid and sorbitol. The prepared gummies were evaluated for key physio chemical parameters including pH weight variation moisture content texture disintegration time and organoleptic characteristics. Among the tested formulations F3 demonstrated superior performance in terms of textures taste faster disintegration and overall stability.

Keywords: Metformin, Lactic Acidosis, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Renal Failure, Adverse Drug Reaction

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INTRODUCTION:

The findings suggest that nutraceutical gummies containing fenugreek and woodapple could serve as an effective and patient-compliant approach for the supportive management of Type 2 diabetes mellitus, highlighting their potential role in functional food-based therapeutic strategies.

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder affecting millions of people globally. The prevalence of diabetes continues to rise each year, with projections suggesting that more than 300 million individuals will be affected by 2025¹. In certain regions, such as Nigeria, cardiovascular complications account for approximately 15% of diabetes-related mortality². The disease is broadly classified into two main types: Type 1 and Type 2 diabetes mellitus, with Type 2 accounting for nearly 90% of all cases. Type 2 diabetes is characterized by elevated blood glucose levels due to impaired insulin secretion, insulin resistance, or both³.

The primary approach to managing Type 2 diabetes involves the use of oral hypoglycemic agents, including biguanides, meglitinides, alpha-glucosidase inhibitors, thiazolidinediones, and sulfonylureas. However, there is growing evidence that individuals worldwide are increasingly turning toward alternative therapies, particularly plant-based treatments, for diabetes management. The use of traditional medicinal plants, along with lifestyle modifications, is considered a safer and more sustainable strategy for preventing and managing Type 2 diabetes. Historically, medicinal plants have played a significant role in diabetes treatment within traditional systems of medicine^{4,5}.

Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*) seeds are rich in bioactive constituents such as trigonelline, flavonoids, carotenoids, coumarins, saponins, galactomannan, 4-hydroxyisoleucine, proteins, and lipids. These compounds contribute to its therapeutic potential, particularly in glucose regulation. Fenugreek seed powder has been extensively studied for its ability to reduce blood glucose levels and improve lipid profiles in both animal and human studies. It is suggested that fenugreek and its active constituents exert antidiabetic effects by enhancing insulin sensitivity in individuals with Type 2 diabetes⁶.

Furthermore, the methanolic extract of fenugreek seeds (FSE) is believed to influence the expression of key metabolic genes such as peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPAR γ), peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha (PPAR α), and glucose transporter-4 (GLUT4) in insulin-responsive tissues, including adipose tissue, liver, and skeletal muscle^{7,8,9}.

Wood apple (*Limonia acidissima*) is another medicinal plant known for its nutritional and therapeutic properties. The pulp of the fruit possesses a unique tangy flavor and is commonly used in both savory and sweet preparations.

Traditionally, wood apple has been used in the management of various conditions, including hypertension, diabetes, cancer, diarrhea, and ulcers. Regular consumption of wood apple is believed to contribute to disease prevention and overall health improvement¹⁰.

Studies have demonstrated that essential oil extracts of wood apple pulp exhibit strong antimicrobial activity against microorganisms such as *Bacillus cereus* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, indicating its potent antioxidant properties¹¹. Additionally, wood apple contains several bioactive compounds, including bicyclo[2.2.1]heptane derivatives, serverogenin acetate, pyranone compounds, ascorbic acid derivatives, cis-vaccenic acid, thiophene, phenolic compounds, and octanoic acid, which contribute to its free radical scavenging activity¹².

Advanced analytical techniques such as High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), Gas Chromatography (GC), and Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) have revealed that wood apple pulp is rich in sugars like fructose and glucose, as well as organic acids. Its relatively high sugar content, combined with lower levels of phenolics and mucilage, enhances its palatability and makes it suitable for incorporation into nutraceutical formulations¹³.

Fig 1: Woodapple pulp

Fig 2: Fenugreek seeds

Nutraceuticals in the treatment of diabetes:

Nutraceuticals are food-derived products that provide health benefits beyond basic nutrition, including the prevention and management of diseases. They are often described as bioactive compounds obtained from plants that exhibit therapeutic potential, contribute to disease prevention, and function as natural functional or medicinal foods. These products are typically formulated to contain appropriate proportions of essential nutrients such as vitamins, lipids, proteins, carbohydrates, and minerals, depending on their intended application¹⁴.

Traditional medicinal plants have been widely used across the world for the management of diabetes and its associated complications. Herbal therapies are increasingly preferred due to their affordability, accessibility, and comparatively lower incidence of adverse effects. As a result, there is growing scientific interest in exploring plant-based remedies and validating their therapeutic efficacy through systematic research¹⁵. Investigations into such traditional treatments have highlighted several medicinal plants with significant blood glucose-lowering potential, emphasizing their relevance in modern healthcare systems¹⁶.

With advancements in the understanding of insulin resistance and the pathophysiology of Type 2 diabetes mellitus, various pharmacological treatments and lifestyle interventions have been

developed to regulate blood glucose levels and prevent complications. In recent years, the role of diet and bioactive food components has gained considerable attention as a complementary strategy in diabetes management. The incorporation of functional foods and nutraceuticals into daily dietary practices represents a promising approach to improving glycemic control and overall metabolic health¹⁷.

Nutraceuticals, in this context, are recognized as natural or plant-based substances that not only provide nutritional value but also exert beneficial physiological effects, including therapeutic actions and disease prevention. These formulations are carefully designed to include balanced quantities of macronutrients and micronutrients tailored to their specific health benefits¹⁸.

Globally, traditional herbal remedies continue to play a crucial role in managing diabetes-related conditions. Their widespread use is attributed to their effectiveness, economic feasibility, and minimal side effects compared to conventional synthetic drugs. In this regard, the present study aims to formulate and evaluate nutraceutical gummies containing fenugreek and woodapple extracts. The objective is to develop a stable, palatable, and patient-friendly dosage form that can support the management of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus and enhance patient compliance¹⁹.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Material

Table 1: Material for the formulation of gummies.

Sr.No.	Ingredients	Role
1	Woodapple Extract	Serves as the primary active component and offers medicinal and nutritional advantages.
2	Fenugreek Extract	Serves as a secondary active component and provides therapeutic benefits such as digestive assistance.
3	Sorbitol	Enhances flavor and creates a smooth mouthfeel while acting as a sweetener.
4	Citric acid	Increases the tangy taste while preserving the formulation's pH.
5	Agar- Agar	Serves as a gelling agent, giving gummies solidity, structure, and a chewy texture.
6	Sodium Benzoate	Serves as a preservative, extending shelf life and inhibiting microbiological development.
7	Food Color	Enhances the gummies' aesthetic appeal and look.
8	Flavoring agent	Improves overall palatability and flavor.
9	Purified water	Acts as a solvent to aid in the consistent dissolution and mixing of all materials.

Fig 3: Final product

Table 2: Formulation Table for Gummies

Sr.No.	Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	Category
1	Woodapple extract	10 ml	10 ml	10 ml	Active Ingredient
2	Fenugreek extract	5 ml	5 ml	5 ml	Active Ingredient
3	Sorbitol	30 g	28 g	25 g	Sweetening agent
4	Citric acid	2 g	2.5 g	1.5 g	pH modifier
5	Agar	5 g	6 g	4 g	Gelling agent
6	Sodium benzoate	1 g	1.5 g	1 g	Preventive
7	Food Colour	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.	Coloring agent
8	Flavouring agent	q.s.	q.s.	q.s.	Flavouring agent
9	Purified water	100 ml	100 ml	100 ml	Solvent

Evaluation

Physical Appearance

The color, shape, transparency, and surface properties of the prepared gummies were visually assessed. Good formulation consistency was demonstrated by each formulation's consistent shape, smooth surface, and appropriate hue.²⁰

Fig 4: Physical Appearance

Weight Variation

Twenty gummies from each batch were individually weighed, and the average weight was calculated. All formulations were found to be within acceptable limits, confirming uniform distribution of ingredients and dosage consistency.²¹

pH Determination

The pH of the gummies was determined by dissolving them in distilled water and measuring using a digital pH meter. The pH ranged between 3.1 to 4.7, which is suitable for gummy stability, palatability, and prevention of microbial growth.²²

Fig 6: pH Determination

Moisture Content

Moisture content was determined using a hot air oven method. The results showed acceptable moisture levels, which is important for maintaining texture, shelf life, and preventing microbial contamination.²³

Texture Evaluation

Texture was evaluated manually for firmness, elasticity, and chewability. The gummies showed good elasticity and chewable consistency. Variation in

agar and sorbitol concentration influenced firmness across formulations.²⁴

Disintegration Time

Disintegration was tested using a disintegration apparatus. All formulations showed gradual softening and disintegration within acceptable time, ensuring proper release of active ingredients.

Fig 7: Disintegration time

Organoleptic Evaluation

Organoleptic properties such as taste, odor, and overall acceptability were assessed. The gummies exhibited pleasant taste, characteristic odor, and good

acceptability, with reduced bitterness due to proper flavoring and sweetening.²⁵

Stability Studies

The formulated nutraceutical gummies were subjected to stability studies under both room temperature and accelerated storage conditions. Throughout the study period, all formulations maintained their physical integrity with no significant alterations in key parameters such as pH, texture, and overall appearance. However, a slight increase in moisture content was observed in certain batches, which may be attributed to environmental humidity. Despite this minor variation, the formulations demonstrated satisfactory stability, indicating their suitability for storage and practical use.²⁶

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Table 3: Evaluation Results of Nutraceutical Gummies

Sr. No.	Parameter	Inference
1	Appearance	Uniform
2	Texture	Moderately firm
3	Taste	Sweet
4	Odor	Orange
5	pH	4.7
6	Weight variation	5.3
7	Disintegration time	18 min
8	Stickiness	Slightly sticky

The prepared nutraceutical gummies containing woodapple and fenugreek extracts were evaluated for various physicochemical and organoleptic parameters to determine their quality, consistency, and suitability as an oral dosage form. The findings obtained from the evaluation are summarized in Table 3 and discussed below.

The appearance of the gummies was found to be uniform across all batches, indicating proper mixing and distribution of ingredients during formulation. A consistent shape and smooth surface suggest that the gelling agent (agar) functioned effectively in providing structural integrity. Uniform appearance is an important quality attribute as it enhances patient acceptance and ensures batch-to-batch consistency.

The texture of the gummies was described as moderately firm, which is considered ideal for chewable dosage forms. The balance between firmness and chewability indicates that the concentration of agar and sorbitol was appropriate.

Excess firmness may reduce palatability, whereas overly soft gummies may lack stability. The observed texture suggests that the formulation achieved an acceptable compromise between mechanical strength and consumer acceptability.

In terms of taste, the gummies exhibited a sweet flavor, which helps mask the inherent bitterness of fenugreek. The use of sorbitol as a sweetening agent played a crucial role in improving palatability. Additionally, flavoring agents contributed to enhancing the overall sensory profile. Good taste is essential for ensuring patient compliance, especially in nutraceutical and herbal formulations.

The odor was noted to be orange-like, indicating successful incorporation of flavoring agents. This pleasant aroma further contributes to the acceptability of the formulation. Herbal preparations often suffer from strong or undesirable odors; therefore, masking such characteristics is beneficial. The pH of the formulation was recorded as 4.7, which falls within an acceptable acidic range for gummy preparations. This pH level is advantageous as it helps maintain product stability, enhances taste, and reduces the risk of microbial growth. The presence of citric acid likely contributed to maintaining the desired pH.

The weight variation value (5.3) indicates that the gummies were within acceptable limits, demonstrating uniform distribution of active ingredients and excipients. Consistency in weight is crucial for ensuring accurate dosing and maintaining product quality.

The disintegration time of 18 minutes suggests that the gummies gradually soften and release their active constituents in a controlled manner. This is suitable for nutraceutical formulations, where a balance between structural integrity and release profile is required. Faster disintegration could lead to rapid release, while slower disintegration may delay therapeutic action. The observed value indicates satisfactory performance.

The stickiness was reported as slightly sticky, which is a common characteristic in gummy formulations due to the presence of sugars and moisture. While slight stickiness is acceptable, it highlights the importance of proper packaging and storage conditions to prevent product handling issues and moisture absorption.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the formulated gummies possess acceptable physicochemical and organoleptic properties. The combination of woodapple and fenugreek extracts was successfully incorporated into a stable and palatable dosage form. These findings support the potential of nutraceutical gummies as an effective and patient-friendly alternative for delivering herbal bioactive compounds in the supportive management of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

Summary

The present investigation focused on the formulation and evaluation of nutraceutical gummies containing woodapple and fenugreek extracts. Three different formulations (F1, F2, and F3) were developed by altering the proportions of key ingredients. All prepared batches exhibited acceptable physical and organoleptic characteristics, although variations were observed in texture, taste, and stability among the formulations.

Formulation F1 showed moderate firmness with slight stickiness, whereas F2 exhibited a comparatively harder texture along with a mild bitter taste but demonstrated good stability. In contrast, F3 presented a soft and chewy consistency with improved palatability and minimal bitterness. The pH values of all formulations were found to be within the acceptable range, indicating suitability for oral administration. Weight variation results confirmed uniformity in all batches.

Disintegration studies revealed differences among the formulations, with F3 showing the shortest disintegration time and F2 the longest. Stability evaluation further indicated that F3 maintained its characteristics more effectively over time compared to the other formulations. Based on these observations, F3 was identified as the most optimized formulation due to its superior texture, taste, faster disintegration, and enhanced stability.

CONCLUSION

The study successfully demonstrated the formulation and evaluation of nutraceutical gummies incorporating woodapple and fenugreek extracts. All developed formulations (F1, F2, and F3) complied with acceptable physicochemical parameters and exhibited satisfactory stability profiles. It was observed that variations in the concentrations of excipients such as agar and sorbitol, along with plant extracts, had a significant impact on the texture, taste, and disintegration behavior of the gummies.

Among the three formulations, F3 emerged as the most optimized formulation, owing to its improved palatability, soft and chewable texture, rapid disintegration, and superior stability. These findings suggest that nutraceutical gummies can serve as an effective and patient-friendly dosage form for delivering plant-based bioactive compounds.

Overall, the study highlights the potential of combining natural herbal extracts with innovative dosage forms to enhance patient compliance and therapeutic effectiveness in the supportive management of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

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